
BEST PRACTICES AND QUALITY LIBRARY SERVICES

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Abstract:

In case of the Library the Librarian has to play very important and vital role. ICT plays important role in the development and best Practices in the sector of Library.

In the 21st century new Trends in Technology development, various ways like microforms, magnetic, apparatus, sound recording films, photos, and anther, Electronic media. In short Library of 21st century becomes paperless Library through internet.

Today so many ICT's are available in the service of Library in following manner.

Internet, News paper clipping service, Digitalization, Electronic reference, Inter Library loan, Electronic document delivery system, Electronic thesis and Dissertation, OPAC, E-Learning, Wi-Fi-Technology, 3m security system, C. C. T. V., Internet Based Service.

NAAC accreditation has truly managed to stir the academic Librarians to assume a proactive role in supporting the cause of higher education which aims at knowledge empowerment of the students.

These models and Techniques play vital role in best practices in the Library service. Internet and related with other facility. The Library works smoothly in day to days communication. According to NAAC the Library is important for all student in 21st century. The Library is not only the book circulation but it is the bank of knowledge. That is the main theme of the best practices of the Library. Library and Information science as an integral part for information profession of not only "Education for all" but also "Tomorrow".

Key Words: *Best Practices, ICT, Internet Based service Librarian Role, Resources.*

Introduction:

In the present day scenario and digital explosion, Library has become very important platform for the sharing new ideas, new information and new knowledge. Library and information services plays vital role in academic institution and research organization for the students, faculty member sand research scholars. Hence, higher education department of India has established NAAC (National accreditation for assessment

council) for improving quality based education in colleges and institutions. In NAAC there is separate section for the library & information services. So library plays on important role in providing right information to the user at right time, and also Library and information system management provides to the user community to indentify & acces the relevant knowledge resources. ¹If Librarian and library staff change their mentality then every library can create

healthy environment for their user in digital Era. (Rao & Babu, 2001) to manage. ²The digital library effectively the information manager should have the knowledge in the field of computer and networking, content manager and information analysis, internet surfing technique, digital resources, websites and organization of data, etc. (Satija MP, 2003)

Definition:

Best practices are a strategy or method that has been commonly acknowledged as between then any choices since it products results that are better than those accomplished by different means. It is utilized to improve quality in the services of any organization.

According to Cambridge English dictionary “Best practices mean a working method or set of working methods that is officially accepted as being the best to use in a particular business or industry, usually describe and formally and in detail. ³The term Information and communication technologic (ICTs) is defined as a diverse set of technological tools and resources used to communicate and create, disseminate, store and manage information Blurton, 1999)

Need of Best Practices:

With and advancement of information communication technology in higher education, the nature of academic libraries has been changed way from traditional library to information centre. Due to information explosion library collection has been replacement in information database also. In this era, library implements some changes in their services and activities library adopts best practices in colleges for the following purposes.

- To fulfill & satisfy user is demand.

- To execute the five laws of library & information service.
- To know user’s need.
- Awareness & marketing of library services & products.

Best Practices in Library Resources and Library Service.

Resource Sharing:

Resource sharing is a term refers to libraries sharing their resources including the sources of information. Staff expertise, infrastructure & finance. Resource sharing works through Library networks & library consortia. It will enhance the usage of collection and services. It improves the access of library services to the users of other academic institution for then learning & for increasing their professional knowledge.

Other Institutional Library Visits:

Library members can visit other institutional libraries to learn activities & services & the ways they adopted for providing better services. The aim of this practice is to adviser library staff members & to overview at the work followed by other institutional libraries. They also it creates awareness and coralihtation among the people. Support from the management & Co-ordination among members is very important for this thing.

Documentation:

The term documentation is the process connected with identification, recording, organization, storage of intellectual content recorded in a document in print or non-point medium. Proper documentation is crucial for the development of any service. In libraries, library staff members have to maintain record of books & other non-book resources. Service records, visitor’s record etc. Accreditation agencies are looking of

the development & statistics of the libraries. Now a day's library has to collect feedback from their users and to analyze it. This response of users is also to be documented.

Library Book Exhibition:

It provides an open platform to faculty members or students and staff members of institution to know recent editions of published books on their area. It also facilitates to review and recommend the books for the library to strengthen the collection. It also helps to develop the reading habits among institute fraternity.

Hand on Training Programme:

The aim of this programme is to educate library staff members to look at the work practice followed by other college libraries. Library staff members can visit other institutional libraries to learn about their library services and activities & the techniques they adopted for providing better services. Library staff can provide quality services to their patrons. Co-ordination among the members is necessary for this activity.

Library Best User Award:

This is very good option as because of this many students can get easily attracted to visit library & use of resources. It increases the user statistics.

Maintenance of Services Areas:

Library is a place where to read. Consult & borrow reading materials, so atmosphere should be clean and calm. It provides suitable atmosphere for reading and searching for the users. Library should provide quiet space for group discussions & research scholars and chairs are important for increasing the comfort level for reading.

User's Feedback:

Through feedback system we can access & increase the quality in services delivered by the library. User's feedback is necessary to understand, what we can improve & make changes according to it.

Information Communication Technology (ICT) based Best Practice:

The term ICT is defined as a diverse set of technological tools and resources used to communicate and create, store and manage information.

ICT in Libraries:

It can be used in libraries and information centres for the development of new information service and computerization of library services. ICT is useful for. –

- Saving the space using the electronic storage.
- Provision of quality information.
- Improving of co-operation in sharing of resources.
- Improving productivity & efficiency of library services effectively.

Today so many ICTs are available in the services of Library of following manner. –

- 1) Library webpage.
- 2) Institutional Repository.
- 3) Computerized Library with Library software.
- 4) Internet.
- 5) Electronic reference.
- 6) News paper clipping service.
- 7) OPAC service
- 8) C. C. T. V.
- 9) Digitalization
- 10) Electrical thesis & Dissertation.
- 11) E-learning
- 12) Inter-Library loan.
- 13) Wi-Fi technology.
- 14) 3 M security System.
- 15) Electronic document delivery system.

Importance of ICT:

ICT presents revolutionary approach to address development. Their capacity has proved to access the information instantly from any location of the world.

1) Library Webpage:

A library webpage or universal Resource Location (URL) facilitates single window access to various web enabled library services. A library website provides a library with a website to offer its services and to tell its story to its community.

2) Institutional Repository:

Library should develop institutional repository of question paper, syllabus, and research papers. Notes etc. can be made available for user community. An institutional repository is an online archives for collecting, preserving digital copies of the intellectual output of an institution.

3) Computerized Library with Library Software:

Software consists of the step-by-step instructions that tell the computer what to do. In a university library the most common computer software's are used such as library automation software, database management software & application software. Many software packages for various applications in the field of library are genlib, solu etc.

4) Internet:

Internet means one of the best network came in to existence with the help of computer technology through search engine Yahoo, Google, Orcute etc. for the development of the library. The following websites are certainly very useful for Librarian.

- 1) Free online Journals
<https://www.jodi.ecs.ston.ac.uk>
- 2) Free online E-Books
<https://www.etext.libvirgina.edu/books>

5) Electronic Reference:

Electronic reference service divided into E-Publishing, E-Learning and E-Document delivery with the advantage of Internet. The ability to share virtual resources, co-operative collection, development through arrangement become popular in this service. There are so many options available like telephone inquiry online inquiry, chat vases virtual reference etc.

6) News Paper Clipping Service:

The option of Dr. Singh Desidock occurred 17 English and Hindi Newspapers. For this service with the help of Internet published papers can read through network. Through this service the Librarian can achieve information and indexing.

7) OPAC:

It is also one of the important service with Library can provide on net. Through net Library resources will be made available worldwide and any one throughout the world can access Library resources. This will raise the status of Library internationally.

8) C. C. T. V.:

With the help of this system the Librarian can observe the total Library with the help of this we can control a crime related with books like a loss of books, thefting, abuse of books etc. it is the best system in case of Library for observation.

9) Digitalization:

There are few books which are very impartment for historical value. While reposition or Xeroxing could not possible that time Digitalization is very important for this type of book. The copy of same book will become stable it can be useful for photographic, pictures, thesis, maps etc.

10) Electronic Thesis and Dissertation:

Now days there are some many research publications available on online service. Indian institute of science institute of science invited this type of project to collect the same material through Electronic thesis and Dissertation of Indian institute of science with the help of the same website. We can search biological science, chemical sci., Mechanical Sci., Physical & mathematical science project.

11) E-Learning:

The information can be accessed by any one, at any time and from anywhere. It is effective and time saving when using information system one is more innovative and interactive. It is a self paced learning. Inter Library Loan (H. L.) is facilitated. Instruction – quality is consistent. The information can be shared by more than one user at a time. It offers an piecemeal learning.

12) Inter Library Loan:

The needs of readers are very important and one Library cannot fulfill the same so there is necessary of Inter Library loan. In Great Britain there is British Library Leading Division (B.L.L.D.). In this system there is on main Library and through this Library the reader can collect the information and knowledge from the Library.

13) Wi-Fi- Technology:

In short the full freedom use of internet is known as “Wi-Fi Technology” with the use of portal system. Through these Technology two computers connected with each other. It is available from 2.4 to 5 GHz Radio Band Frequency.

14) 3M Security System:

This system includes the following magnetic tools.

- i) Security strips.
- ii) 3M diction system.
- iii) 3M sensitizing machine.
- iv) 3M self check out machine.

These systems are very useful for the security of the books. Through these systems, we can avoid the loss of books. It is also useful for the circulation of the books. At the time of stock verification with help of scanner. We can confirm whether the book is available or not.

15) Electronic Document Delivery System:

Access to full text E-Journals / data base. The user demand to access information at their desktops that too into electronic journals electronic journals are available journals; 1. locally held electronic journals; These include full texts to journals covered by ABI / INFORM of Bell+Howell, and more 2. Electronic journals in Internet base databases; these include over 7000 journals held in the Proquest Direct of Bell + Howell 3. Consortia's like UGC Infonet CeRA, INDEST are also available.

Internet based Services; The internet has become the most largest flow of information and has provided the various services to the user like-mail chat list serves remote log on free journal services, virtual reference desk subject portals and gateways electronic publishing services business and trade information, TOC service, blogging Bulletin board, Push and Pull services, OPAC housekeeping operation full text downloads etc.

NAAC accreditation has truly managed to stir the academic Librarians to assume a pro-active role in supporting the cause of higher education which aims at knowledge empowerment of the student. ⁴“LIS professionals need to play a crucial role in the education process by making people aware of a need and motivating the use of information a new knowledge. For successful implementation of digital library.” (Krishnamurthy, M. 2005)

Conclusion:

These models and Techniques play vital role in best practices in the Library service, Internet and related with other facility. The Library works smoothly in day to days communication, According to NAAC the Library is important for all student in 21st century. The Library is not only the book circulation but it is the bank of knowledge. That is the main theme of the best practices of the Library. Library and Information science as an integral part for information profession of not only “Education for all” but also “Tomorrow”

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